

The background is a dark blue space filled with white stars of varying sizes. Several stylized planets are visible: a large orange planet in the top left, a small cratered planet in the top center, a large planet with orange and red horizontal stripes on the right, and a large planet with orange, brown, and blue horizontal stripes on the bottom left.

FROM PINK TOWER

TO CUBE SAT

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INNOVATION LAB

Blue
Blocks

DRONE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION CENTER

SpacELAB

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BLUE BLOCKS MONTESSORI SCHOOL
Student Led
CUBE SATELLITE MISSION
Authorized By

...erwriter and Joint Bookman...

SBB-2

10 × 10 × 10 cm

WHY?

Expensive

Cheap

In space

Fold small. Launch cheap. Deploy large.

HOW IT WORKS

Goes up

Lid opens

Fold out

Burns

Opens

One action. Done.

(Combined panel version - delete 5 GIFs if using this)

WHAT WE'RE SOLVING

Over the next 3 months:

1

MATERIAL

What survives
space?

2

FOLD

What's not
patented?

3

RELEASE

How to let
go?

4

ONE SHOT

Deploy in
one action?

These are the challenges we're working on.

Deployment from Launch Vehicle

Montessori children who built the Pink Tower at three
are building a satellite at thirteen.

A vibrant space-themed background featuring a dark blue starry sky. In the top left, a brown, cratered planet is visible. In the top right, a meteor with a yellow and orange trail is streaking across the sky. The bottom left shows a portion of a planet with orange, red, and green horizontal bands. The bottom right shows a portion of a reddish-orange planet with darker spots. Several white, four-pointed starburst graphics are scattered throughout the scene.

Thank you